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Review of corrosion and ageing issues of materials (SoA) and critical parameters defined

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Partner name: University of Leicester (ULEIC)

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
PCM	Phase Change Material
ETES	Electro-Thermal Energy Storage
RE	Renewable Electricity
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
SME	Small to Medium Enterprise
ORC	Organic Rankine Cycle
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
EDS	Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy
XRD	X-ray Diffraction
UV	Ultraviolet

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1. About the project

SEHRENE's innovative Electrothermal Energy Storage (ETES) concept is designed to efficiently store renewable electricity (RE) and heat, which can be delivered when needed. With an energy efficiency of 80-85 %, it is geographically flexible, free of critical raw materials, and offers storage durations 8-12 times longer than lithium-ion batteries. Its Levelized Cost of Storage ranges between €80-137/MWh depending on the use case, making it more economical than pumped hydro, the lowest-cost commercial electricity storage option. Additionally, its 20-30-years lifespan is 2-3 times longer than lithium-ion batteries.

A TRL4 prototype and digital twins of three full use cases will be developed: (i) a ceramics plant storing excess on-site photovoltaic power and industrial waste heat within a microgrid to continuously produce green hydrogen and to utilise the stored electricity for self-consumption, (ii) a smart grid, and (iii) a geothermal power plant. The ETES solution integrates: (i) a novel heat pump with a coefficient of performance reaching 50 % of the theoretical maximum, (ii) a novel thermal energy storage system with an energy density of 90 kWh/m³ (+30 %), utilising phase change material (PCM) within a novel metallic Kelvin-cell-like foam, and (iii) an Organic Rankine Cycle operating under innovative parameters. New digital tools will optimise energy management and support investment decisions by incorporating life cycle assessment and techno-economic factors.

SEHRENE brings together a consortium of five top-tier R&D teams specialising in prototyping, physics-based modelling, characterisation, and digital twins for thermo-electric systems, thermal storage, and AI-driven energy management. It also includes a renewable energy producer, a distribution system operator, a ceramics manufacturer, a small-to-medium enterprise (SME) specialising in decision-support tools, and another SME focused on dissemination and communication. The list of consortium partners participating in the SEHRENE project is provided in Table 1. The exploitation strategy aims to implement this solution in its first factory by 2029, with plans to capture 1 % of the market by 2040, avoiding the use of 90 million cubic meters of natural gas and reducing CO₂ emissions by 15 million tons annually. By 2035, the R&D

and industrial partners expect to generate €5.8 million in revenue from heat pump and thermal storage sales, ORC systems, R&D result licenses, and consulting services.

In summary, SEHRENE offers a groundbreaking ETES solution that addresses a key challenge of conventional systems – temperature loss reducing round-trip efficiency. This disruptive design not only resolves this issue but also positions itself as a vital enabler of Europe’s energy transition goals.

Table 1. The list of consortium partners participating in the SEHRENE project.

S.No.	Participant Name
1	Commissariat à L'Énergie Atomique et aux Énergies Alternatives (CEA)
2	University of Liège (ULIÈGE)
3	Politecnico di Milano (POLIMI)
4	Turboden (TURBODEN)
5	Fundación Circe Centro de Investigación de Recursos y Consumos Energéticos (CIRCE)
6	Torreced SA (TORRECID)
7	Zorlu Enerji Elektrik Uretim AS (ZOREN)
8	Cuerva Energia SLU (CUERVA)
9	Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação (SPI)
10	Technovative Solutions ltd (TVS)
11	University of Leicester (ULEIC)

2. Executive summary

Selecting a PCM for a latent thermal energy storage system requires consideration of several criteria, including thermophysical properties (such as melting temperature, melting enthalpy, and ageing behaviour), safety aspects (e.g., toxicity), and economic factors (cost and availability). This deliverable provides a comprehensive state-of-the-art review with a particular focus on ageing and corrosion issues associated with PCMs. It also identifies and defines the critical parameters relevant to these two aspects, offering valuable insights for material selection and system optimisation.

Ageing and corrosion processes occurring in thermal storage systems that use phase change materials are inherently complex. This complexity arises from several factors: the wide variety of PCM compositions, the diversity of structural materials in contact with these PCMs, and the varying operational conditions under which these systems function. These variables can significantly impact system performance and durability.

Given these challenges, it is essential to conduct tailored preliminary tests designed for specific materials and operational conditions in each system, focusing on ageing and corrosion issues. These tests will provide critical insights into the compatibility and longevity of the components, ensuring safe and efficient scaling up to industrial applications.

3. Introduction

Within the SEHRENE project, a latent thermal energy storage (TES) system is being developed for testing in a prototype, integrated with a heat pump and an ORC. These latent heat storage systems utilise PCM to store heat at an almost constant temperature level through phase transitions, which is why they are referred to as PCM modules throughout this document.

The proposed design features a shell-and-tube heat exchanger with a single-pass flow on the tube side. To enhance thermal conductivity on the PCM side, an alveolar aluminium matrix is incorporated around the tubes. (For further technical details on this technology, refer to D4.1 of the project, titled "*PCM Selection for ETES*").

The selection of PCM for latent TES systems requires consideration of multiple criteria, including thermophysical properties (e.g., melting temperature, melting enthalpy, ageing characteristics, corrosion resistance, and supercooling behaviour), safety considerations (e.g., toxicity), and economic factors (e.g., cost and availability).

This deliverable aims to provide a comprehensive state-of-the-art review focusing specifically on ageing and corrosion challenges associated with PCMs and to define the critical parameters that must be addressed for these two key issues.

4. Ageing of PCMs

The selection of PCMs plays a crucial role in determining the long-term efficiency of TES systems. Ensuring the stability of PCMs, especially their composition, latent heat and melting points, when

maintained at high temperature during a long time, or over repeated charge/discharge cycles, is essential for maintaining system performance. Over time, the ageing of PCMs can lead to significant performance degradation [1]. Firman *et al.* [2] observed that thermal ageing of beeswax reduced the discharge rate by 23.2 %, resulting in over 50 % decrease in power output and storage efficiency. In contrast, paraffin wax showed lower degradation, with a 14.7 % reduction in discharge rate and an 18.7 % decrease in power output, whilst maintaining a higher efficiency of 67.2 % compared to 41.1 % for beeswax. These results highlight the varied impacts of ageing on different PCMs, emphasising the importance of careful material selection to optimise long-term storage capacity and efficiency [3]. Therefore, it is critical to evaluate PCMs for long-term performance and safety when developing TES systems [4]. Different aspects/issues with the ageing of PCMs are summarised below.

4.1 Mechanisms of PCM degradation

The degradation of PCMs in TES systems arises from several mechanisms. One prominent issue is the evaporation due to high vapour pressure; particularly in organic PCMs, high vapour pressures at elevated temperatures can result in material loss, ultimately destabilising the PCM composition. Katish *et al.* [5] investigated the thermal stability of several PCMs, including hexadecane, heptadecane, octadecane, RT18, RT22, and RT25. Their study found that at 30 °C, none of the PCMs exhibited measurable mass loss, highlighting their stability at lower temperatures and suitability for such conditions. However, as temperatures exceeded 150 °C, gradual mass loss began, ranging from 15 % to 20 %, likely due to thermal degradation and volatilisation effects. At 175 °C, the majority of these PCMs retained a large proportion of their initial mass even after enduring 10,000 thermal cycles, suggesting strong thermal resilience under repeated heating and cooling. However, between 250 °C and 350 °C, mass retention declined sharply, with nearly complete mass loss observed around 300 °C. Bayón *et al.* [6] observed that approximately 80 % of the initial mass of D-mannitol was lost when it was melted at 180 °C in the air over a period of up to 16 days. This demonstrates the necessity of selecting PCMs that match the intended temperature range for each application.

Thermal degradation is another critical mechanism, particularly in high-temperature applications. PCMs subjected to high thermal cycling are prone to decomposition, forming new chemical species that can compromise thermal stability and storage efficiency over time. For example, D-mannitol, when melted at 180 °C in air, began transforming after seven days into a dark-brown, sticky paste through caramelisation processes similar to those in sugars, which failed to solidify upon cooling [6]. Analysis revealed the formation of three distinct products from this brown polymeric material, likely containing carbonyl groups, enolic groups, or α , β -unsaturated carbonyl groups. To mitigate thermal degradation, ageing experiments on D-mannitol were also conducted under inert atmospheres, such as argon (Ar) [6] and nitrogen (N₂) [7]. However, strong browning was observed after 16 days, accompanied by a change in appearance to a soft, sticky paste and a reduction in initial mass, suggesting that the inert atmosphere did not show any improvement. On the contrary, a binary mixture of caprylic acid and cetyl alcohol with a eutectic composition at an 85:15 molar ratio demonstrated no changes in chemical structure after undergoing 200 melting/freezing cycles [8]. This stability was attributed to the significant difference between its melting and decomposition temperatures. Similarly, the erythritol-vermiculite form-stable PCM remained stable even after 300 melting/freezing cycles [9]. This demonstrates that it is important to understand the stability ranges of the PCMs to be used and unless PCMs are proven stable, they should not be used in TES applications.

Chemical reaction with environmental factors, such as oxygen, water vapour, and metals within heat exchangers, is another factor that can significantly impact PCM stability. For instance, molten nitrate salts, under the typical operating temperature of 560 °C and oxygen partial pressure of 0.2 atm, decompose to produce a nitrite content of 4.5 mol % [10]. Elevated temperatures can lead to further decomposition reactions, primarily involving the breakdown of nitrite ions into oxide ions (e.g., O²⁻) and various gaseous species, including nitrous gases (NO, NO₂), nitrogen (N₂), and oxygen (O₂) [11]. These kinds of decomposition reactions are particularly concerning because of the release of toxic nitrous gases [12] and the formation of oxide ions can exacerbate the corrosion of the structural material [13,14]. The eutectic

mixture of molten chloride salts, $\text{MgCl}_2/\text{KCl}/\text{NaCl}$, is known to exhibit strong hydrophilic behaviour when exposed to atmospheric moisture. This interaction leads to the formation of oxide and hydroxide impurities upon heating, which in turn initiates the corrosion of the container materials [15]. This salt mixture can also interact with 316 stainless steel (at 700 °C), used as the structural material. This causes the dissolution of Cr, Ni, and Fe species into the molten salt. This dissolution is attributed to the hydrolysis of MgCl_2 , which generates MgO and gaseous HCl . The HCl gas permeates the environment around and reacts with the inner surface of 316 stainless steel to produce metal chlorides (CrCl_2 , NiCl , and FeCl_2). These metallic chlorides subsequently integrate into the molten salt, altering its composition and negatively impacting its chemical compatibility and performance [16].

The separation of components in mixtures or the occurrence of incongruent melting presents another considerable challenge, as different constituents in a PCM blend may melt and solidify at varying rates. This phenomenon can lead to phase separation, altering the phase change temperatures and diminishing the PCM blend's effective heat storage capacity. For instance, sodium acetate trihydrate exhibits incongruent melting, where instead of forming a uniform melt of the trihydrate, phase segregation occurs, resulting in the precipitation of anhydrous sodium acetate from the solution [17]. To mitigate this issue, strategies such as incorporating low concentrations of polymer additives have been employed to suppress phase segregation in sodium acetate trihydrate [18].

4.2 Ageing tests

The above insights underscore the importance of conducting thorough ageing tests to evaluate the stability of PCMs before their deployment in TES applications. The following sub-sections outline the procedures and measurement techniques employed to evaluate the stability of PCMs.

4.2.1 Procedures

To understand and mitigate PCM ageing, a variety of ageing test procedures are employed. One common approach is thermal cycling – repeatedly subjecting the PCM to alternating high and low temperatures to simulate prolonged use [19,20]. PCMs are cycled between temperatures where they fully crystallise at the

lower limit and fully melt at the upper limit. This cycling is often conducted under either normal atmospheric conditions or controlled inert atmospheres, such as argon or nitrogen, to observe the effects of oxidation [6,7]. Another approach involves maintaining the PCM at a constant high temperature for an extended period, allowing the observation of changes in stability under persistent thermal stress [21–23]. These tests should also be conducted under either normal atmospheric conditions or controlled inert atmospheres, such as argon or nitrogen, to evaluate the effects of oxidation.

4.2.2 Measurements

Measurements taken during ageing tests include visual inspection for changes in colour, viscosity, and homogeneity, all of which serve as qualitative indicators of degradation [24]. Mass loss measurements using techniques like thermogravimetric analysis can help quantify material degradation over time, providing insights into the volatility and stability of the PCM [6]. Techniques like high-resolution mass spectrometry, ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy, and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy can help in understanding the chemical decomposition of the PCMs over time [6,25,26]. Gas chromatography can be employed to identify the presence of degradation products [27]. Additionally, differential scanning calorimetry can provide critical insights into the latent heat of phase change, which reflects the energy storage capacity, and the temperature range of the phase change, essential for assessing the PCM's suitability for specific thermal management applications [25,27,28].

4.3 Impact of ageing

The ageing of PCMs in TES applications significantly impacts their performance and reliability. Ageing manifests through various forms of degradation, including changes in appearance, latent heat of fusion, temperature ranges for fusion and crystallisation, and mass loss, all of which compromise energy storage efficiency and long-term stability.

One of the most evident effects of ageing is the change in appearance, such as alterations in colour, viscosity, and homogeneity, which often signal chemical degradation or phase separation [6,7]. Environmental interactions, such as exposure to oxygen and moisture, exacerbate degradation, leading to

oxidation or hydrolysis, which further deteriorates PCM quality [15]. The interaction of PCM with the container materials can further degrade PCM quality. For instance, molten nitrate salts experienced discolouration due to chromium leaching from alloy steels, turning from clear to yellow [15,29].

Ageing also affects the latent heat of fusion, a critical parameter for energy storage efficiency. Over extended use, PCMs can experience declines in latent heat due to thermal and chemical degradation [2,6]. Whilst organic PCMs like paraffin wax and erythritol have demonstrated excellent stability at 70 °C and 130 °C, respectively, maintaining consistent latent heat values after 1000 thermal cycles [20], inorganic PCMs and certain fatty acids, such as stearic acid, have shown irregular declines attributed to impurities or decomposition during cycling [30,31]. Such reductions diminish the material's energy storage capacity and efficiency.

The temperature ranges for fusion and crystallisation, essential for maintaining predictable thermal responses, also shift due to ageing. Prolonged use can lead to broadening or shifting of these ranges, reducing the PCM's effectiveness in its designated application. Sodium acetate trihydrate, for instance, exhibits incongruent melting, resulting in phase segregation and altered phase change temperatures [17]. Although strategies like adding polymer additives can mitigate this issue [18], these shifts underscore the challenges ageing poses to PCM performance.

Mass loss is another critical indicator of PCM ageing, often resulting from evaporation or decomposition [5,6]. Such mass loss not only reduces the material quantity but also destabilises the PCM composition, further compromising its effectiveness. Thermal degradation, a common consequence of ageing, leads to the formation of new chemical species that negatively impact PCM performance. High-temperature PCMs, such as molten nitrate and chloride salts, are particularly prone to decomposition [10–12]. Similarly, chloride salts interact with container materials, causing the dissolution of metals like chromium and nickel, which alters the PCM's composition and accelerates material failure [15,16]. These chemical reactions highlight the need for careful control of operational conditions to minimise degradation.

In summary, the ageing of PCMs results in significant deterioration across multiple properties, including appearance, thermal stability, and chemical composition. These changes reduce the material's energy storage efficiency, reliability, and lifespan. To ensure the suitability of PCMs for long-term TES applications, comprehensive testing, including accelerated thermal cycling and chemical analysis, is essential. Strategies to mitigate ageing effects, such as enhancing PCM formulations and controlling environmental interactions, are crucial for improving their durability and performance [8,27,32–36].

5. Corrosion compatibility of metals and alloys with PCMs

The compatibility between structural materials and the PCM is crucial to ensuring the long operational life of a TES system [37]. The interaction between the PCM and the storage material plays a significant role, especially the corrosion aspect as corrosion can degrade both the performance and longevity of the TES container [38]. Corrosion leads to thinning and weakening of materials, making them brittle and prone to collapse. Generally, organic PCMs pose minimal corrosion risk, except for a few cases. However, most inorganic PCMs are highly corrosive [37]. Ensuring a long service life for the TES system is paramount because the system's life cycle significantly impacts the overall environmental benefits of renewable energy [39]. Among PCMs, organic ones typically exhibit the least corrosion when in contact with heat exchanger materials. In contrast, alternatives like eutectics, and salt hydrates can cause corrosion of metal components, such as containers and heat exchangers [40]. Studies on molten nitrate salts and other high-temperature PCMs have revealed that prolonged exposure to elevated temperatures can lead to degradation, as seen in molten salt systems where nitrate salts decompose into nitrites, increasing their corrosive nature [41]. Metals like stainless steel 316L, when subjected to thermal cycling in molten salts, showed changes in composition due to the dissolution of chromium and nickel oxides [42].

5.1 The process of corrosion

Corrosion is a complex chemical and electrochemical phenomenon that leads to the deterioration of materials, particularly metals and their alloys, due to interactions with their environment. At its core, the

process involves redox reactions where the metal acts as the anode, losing electrons, whilst a reduction reaction occurs at the cathodic site. Key parameters influencing this process include temperature, pH, oxygen availability, humidity, and the presence of aggressive ions such as chlorides [43]. These factors can either accelerate or inhibit corrosion depending on the material and environmental conditions. For instance, an increase in temperature typically enhances the rate of corrosion due to higher reaction kinetics, whereas pH variations can shift the balance between corrosion and passivation. The thermodynamic and kinetic aspects of corrosion, including activation energy and Gibbs free energy, play crucial roles in determining whether a material is susceptible to corrosion under given conditions [43–45].

5.2 Corrosion tests

5.2.1 Procedures

To evaluate the susceptibility of materials to corrosion, various tests are performed under controlled laboratory conditions. One standard approach involves immersing material samples in the liquid phase of PCMs contained within airtight bottles. These samples are maintained at a constant temperature for a specified period to assess corrosion under static conditions [46]. Another procedure employs thermal cycling, where material samples are alternately heated and cooled whilst immersed in the PCM [47]. This approach simulates real-world applications where PCMs experience phase transitions and temperature fluctuations. Both static and thermal cycling tests help identify the roles of temperature, phase change, and exposure duration on material degradation. Stress corrosion testing may also be considered, where mechanical stresses are applied to the material whilst it is exposed to corrosive environments [48]. Techniques such as U-bend tests or slow strain rate tests are commonly used to study the synergistic effects of mechanical stress and corrosion on material performance [49].

5.2.2 Measurements

Several metrics and methods are used to quantify and analyse corrosion. The most common method involves measuring the mass loss of a material sample after exposure to the corrosive medium [50,51]. This

data is used to calculate the corrosion rate, often expressed in millimetres per year (mm/year), using the formula given in Equation 1.

$$\text{Corrosion Rate (mm/year)} = \frac{(K \times W)}{(A \times T \times D)} \quad (1)$$

Where K is a constant, W is the mass loss (in g), A is the surface area (in cm²), T is the exposure time (in h), and D is the material density (in g/cm³).

Visualisation techniques such as scanning electron microscopy and atomic force microscopy are employed to examine surface morphology and identify localised features like pitting or cracks [52]. Microscopy provides detailed insights into the mechanisms of corrosion and the material's failure modes. Energy dispersive spectroscopy can help in understanding the chemical composition of the corrosion products [53]. Additionally, monitoring the pH of the PCM or surrounding environment is critical. Changes in pH can indicate the progression of corrosion and the release of ions into the medium. For example, a decrease in pH might signal the production of acidic by-products, which can further accelerate the corrosion process [43].

5.3 Impacts of corrosion

Corrosion is a critical concern for materials, particularly when interacting with PCMs in TES applications. These materials can exacerbate localised forms of corrosion such as pitting. Pitting corrosion, characterised by the formation of small but deep cavities, arises when protective oxide layers on metals break down, often under the influence of aggressive ions like chlorides present in some PCMs. Once initiated, these pits can propagate rapidly, undermining the structural integrity of the material [54].

Furthermore, the cyclic thermal behaviour inherent to PCMs can aggravate corrosion mechanisms. Repeated heating and cooling cycles can induce thermal stresses and cause microstructural changes in the material, potentially accelerating crack formation. These cracks, especially when coupled with

environmental stressors or high-pressure conditions, can lead to leaks, ruptures, or even catastrophic failures in critical systems like heat exchangers, storage vessels, and pipelines [52].

In addition, corrosion by-products such as oxides, hydroxides, or salts often form on metal surfaces. Whilst these products might temporarily slow further corrosion by forming passive layers, they can also foster localised attack by creating differential aeration cells. The dynamic interaction between PCMs and corroding surfaces magnifies these effects, requiring stringent material selection and protective measures [37,52,55].

Ultimately, the presence of PCMs and their associated corrosive potential significantly shortens the operational lifespan of metallic components, increasing the demand for proactive maintenance, advanced corrosion-resistant materials, and effective inhibition strategies to mitigate these detrimental effects.

5.4 Known compatibility

Salt hydrates, though prone to corrosion, are particularly suitable for heat storage due to their high latent heat of fusion, good thermal conductivity, and low cost. To mitigate corrosion, PCMs are often encapsulated, and various metal containers have been tested for their thermal conductivity and mechanical resistance. The long-term compatibility of metals with PCMs depends on minimising undesirable interactions, typically evaluated through the corrosion rate. Studies have shown that aluminium is the most compatible container material for many PCMs, demonstrating low mass loss and minimal surface deterioration after long exposure.

For instance, Calabrese *et al.* [52] found that aluminium alloys showed good corrosion stability with magnesium nitrate hexahydrate, whilst carbon steel and copper alloys displayed significant corrosion after only a few hours. Moreno *et al.* [56] tested various metals like copper, aluminium, stainless steel, and carbon steel with different PCMs and concluded that stainless steel and aluminium are generally the most compatible materials for use with many PCMs, although the choice of material depends on the specific PCM application.

Some studies, such as Marín *et al.* [55], revealed that stainless steel is the most resistant to corrosion across a range of PCMs, with minimal mass loss and low corrosion rates. Aluminium also showed good performance with organic PCMs but was prone to corrosion when used with certain inorganic PCMs. Copper, commonly used for its high thermal conductivity, showed corrosion in contact with certain PCMs, although protective coatings can mitigate this issue.

Various studies, including those by Cabeza *et al.* [57], have investigated the compatibility of metals like aluminium, brass, copper, steel, and stainless steel with different PCMs. Stainless steel consistently showed good compatibility with salt hydrates across a range of temperatures, making it a preferred material for PCM storage containers. However, other metals, like aluminium and copper, were found to be suitable under specific conditions depending on the PCM and operating temperature.

Nagano *et al.* [58] and Ushak *et al.* [55] similarly observed that stainless steel (SUS316) and aluminium performed well in corrosion tests with salt hydrates and magnesium nitrate hexahydrate. In contrast, severe corrosion was noted at the salt-air interface for other metals. Additionally, Dindi *et al.* [59] demonstrated that a boron nitride coating effectively prevented corrosion on stainless steel when exposed to molten aluminium-silicon alloy, remaining stable over 720 cycles of melting and solidification.

Paul *et al.* [60] explored materials suitable for use in adipic acid-based PCM storage systems, identifying stainless steel (316L) as a strong candidate due to its performance in short-term corrosion tests. However, whilst 316L stainless steel exhibits excellent corrosion resistance, its higher cost compared to carbon steel presents a challenge for cost-effective system design. Therefore, the balance between material performance and economic considerations must be carefully evaluated when selecting materials for PCM systems.

6. Critical parameters

As described above, several critical parameters dictate the stability and performance of PCMs in thermal energy systems, starting with the environmental conditions in which they operate. The surrounding atmosphere – whether normal air, humid air, or an inert environment such as nitrogen or argon – can dramatically alter PCM stability [32]. Moisture in particular can accelerate corrosive reactions, whereas an

inert atmosphere tends to preserve material integrity over extended periods [15]. The presence of impurities within the PCM is another key parameter; impurities often lead to increased reactivity, which can facilitate unwanted chemical interactions with container materials and result in corrosion [16]. Purification strategies have been shown to mitigate these effects, thereby extending PCM lifespan [29]. Temperature and pressure play a pivotal role in PCM degradation; high temperatures that exceed the decomposition thresholds of PCMs can lead to substantial breakdown, altering their latent heat properties and diminishing storage capacity [54]. Chemical compatibility with encapsulation materials is also essential; for instance, the interaction between the PCM and container alloys, such as aluminium or stainless steel, impacts the durability of the system [37]. Long-term exposure, or duration of high-temperature stability, also influences PCM performance, as prolonged high temperatures can amplify degradation effects [23,61]. Additionally, the number of melting and crystallisation cycles affects the thermal properties of PCMs, with each cycle potentially impacting latent heat values and crystallisation behaviours, especially in high-stress conditions [27,31,62].

7. Proposed actions in SEHRENE project

Table 2 below outlines the proposed actions planned for down-selecting the PCM and construction material for the TES system. The table also details the subsequent actions that will be undertaken on the down-selected PCM and construction material to achieve an in-depth understanding of PCM stability and PCM/material compatibility.

Table 2. The proposed actions planned for down-selecting the PCM and construction material for the TES system.

Step 1	
Corrosion tests: To keep different metal alloys immersed in PCM at 130 °C for one week	
Alloys to be tested	PCMs to be used
Al alloy	A118
Stainless steel	Erythritol
Carbon steel	MgCl ₂ .6H ₂ O
Step 2	
Characterisation of the samples before and after exposure: SEM, EDS, XRD, profilometry, corrosion rate	
Step 3	
The down-selected combination of the PCM and metal alloy will be tested for its stress corrosion behaviour	
The down-selected PCM will be studied for its degradation after ageing using techniques like UV-vis	

8. Summary and future outlook

This report provides the state-of-the-art of ageing and corrosion issues of PCM for latent thermal energy storage systems. It stresses the significance of PCM stability over repeated charge/discharge cycles, as thermal ageing can significantly degrade performance. Corrosion/materials compatibility between PCMs and storage materials is discussed, with findings indicating that stainless steel is often preferred for its compatibility with various PCMs, particularly salt hydrates, but not used so often due to costs.

Ageing and corrosion processes occurring in thermal storage systems that use phase change materials are inherently complex. This complexity arises from several factors: the wide variety of PCM compositions, the diversity of structural materials in contact with these PCMs, and the varying operational conditions under which these systems function. These variables can significantly impact system performance and durability.

Given these challenges, it is essential to conduct tailored preliminary tests designed for each system's specific materials and operational conditions, focusing on ageing and corrosion issues. These tests will provide critical insights into the compatibility and longevity of the components, ensuring safe and efficient scaling up to industrial applications.

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